

THE ADVANTAGES OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN ENHANCING THE EFFICIENCY OF AGRICULTURAL ENTERPRISES

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Abstract: This study examined the effects of digitalization technology shift on rural entrepreneurship and described mitigating efforts using exploratory sequential mixed methodologies. The application of the policy acceptance model method reduced the ambiguity of the analysis of entrepreneurial activity patterns. Data collection methods included semi-structured interviews, questionnaires, and ethnographic observations. The results showed that many new opportunities are created by the technology change and digitization of rural business. These include family-owned enterprises, equitable job opportunities, and regional economic growth.

Keywords: digitalization technology, rural entrepreneurship, sustainability, inequality.

Introduction

Strategies for regional and global development should give priority to the growing importance of digitalizing rural entrepreneurship. It presents fresh opportunities and challenges based on the potential of local knowledge in a rural social solidarity economy (SSE) transformation model. Digitalization also boosts economic growth and the possibilities for regional development. However, mainly the negative sides of this topic have been discussed. The economy benefits from digital technology, but generating value necessitates recognizing the opportunities it presents [1].

The significant changes that digital platforms, infrastructure, and technology have brought about in terms of new job opportunities and entrepreneurial innovation will have an impact on future study subjects. Digitalization technology has the potential to control and positively impact the environment in rural areas. However, it may also exacerbate social inequality and disrupt welfare. Digitalization technology creates new job opportunities and boosts economic growth, but it also increases inequality and labor market concerns. It is still feasible to optimize the positive impacts while reducing the negative ones, despite previous studies showing

that global digital inequality still exists. Therefore, studies on reducing the negative impacts could provide insightful information and policy suggestions for bridging the digital divide in rural regions. [3].

Literature Review

Recent research indicates that many family-run businesses have been inspired to innovate by developing new business models as a result of the way digital technology is transforming entrepreneurship and connecting enterprises. However, these advancements have also resulted in a number of digital disadvantages and gaps, including those between rural and urban areas, gender, age, and ethnic disparity, and disability. The theory of the potential for digitalization technologies in rural entrepreneurship has highlighted the changes influencing entrepreneurial behavior. However, it is believed that the existing theory is insufficient. According to Steininger et al. (2022), there is little microeconomic data regarding how government actions affect the development and growth of digital entrepreneurship. Consequently, research on the core microeconomic data that this work describes is required to close this gap [9].

Research has indicated that the digitalization of rural areas has influenced diverse and adaptable attitudes, behaviors, and skills, even though there are still opportunities to use digital technology. For the majority of small farmers globally, digitalization of rural entrepreneurship could reduce extreme poverty and food insecurity.

Digital technology has been the driving force behind empirical advances in innovative and entrepreneurial strategies. It could promote collective economic activity and increase the private worth of enhanced public assets. However, research has shown that, given the socioeconomic changes impacting individuals, companies, ecosystems, and society at large, we need to broaden our knowledge of digital technology. Understanding should incorporate cross-level analyses, ideas, and concepts from other fields that particularly recognize the significance of digital technology [8].

Previous studies supporting this theory showed that networks could be a valuable source of resources for entrepreneurs. These networks have a strong positive correlation with the survival and growth of businesses. In one previous network theory study, digital technology was included as a moderating variable. It aimed to prove that adopting digital technology is essential to succeed in the fast-paced, entrepreneurial business world of today. This study stands out because it examined the drawbacks of novel, imaginative business model ideas in local social entrepreneurship, each of which has its own set of rules, restrictions, advantages, and disadvantages [2].

Metodology

Traditional methods for evaluating environmental sustainability are mostly impacted by uncertainty. This led to the creation of a case study that used exploratory sequential mixed methodologies. The strategy was focused on directing the objectives in order to examine and ascertain the dual impacts of digitalization technology on sustainable rural entrepreneurship and inequality. The objective was to identify ways to reduce the negative impacts. Additionally, this hybrid approach was used to carry out two steps: generalization, measurement, and authenticity of context. The first step was analyzing the qualitative data using the exploratory design process. In the second stage, an explanatory design was employed to explain quantitative data [4].

To measure and analyze the awareness and behavioral change of policy institutions and entrepreneurial business actors, the study used the experimental theoretical policy acceptance model (PAM) technique. This method reduced the likelihood of making ambiguous interpretations of invisible, non-generalizable, and consistent behavioral patterns. This study initially examined the key elements affecting rural entrepreneurship's technological transformation and digitization. The sequential approach began with a qualitative phase that examined the entrepreneurial business practices of rural areas in relation to digitalization technology. Our exploratory sequential mixed methods methodology integrates and synergizes data sources to examine the main problem and the adoption of digital technologies in complex and dynamic rural areas [6].

Primary data was collected through surveys, semi-structured interviews, and ethnographic observations of rural business owners. The next approach was semi-structured. In line with the exploratory strategy, purposeful and snowball sampling were used to assess the primary quantitative data in more detail. However, in the next phase of the qualitative investigation, the variable related to the impact of digitalization technologies on entrepreneurship was not relevant. This necessitated the use of the exploratory design method in the second stage. Following the analysis of the data from the first stage, the subsequent quantitative step was developed using the knowledge gained, and this manuscript was constructed upon it. A simple random sampling method was used to collect quantitative data for respondents who were all the same. Though it might be applied scientifically, the processing was still in the experimental model stage [7]. To strengthen the analysis and improve the validity and reliability of the data, these deficiencies were addressed through the implementation of a systematic literature study approach.

Results and Discussion

The rural settlements under study have grown as a result of developments in digital technologies. Even in rural areas, the transition to digital technology has changed how individuals behave economically. Analog technology has given way

to digital technology in the economy, affecting sustainable business systems, consumption, and manufacturing. However, the unequal and cruel advancement of digital technology has led to a rise in inequality. Digital technology in rural development may have reduced inequality between rural and urban communities [10]. However, this study did not focus on the difference in inequality in rural and urban areas.

The administration and residents have tried to mitigate the negative impacts by installing internet network equipment in the community. However, this effort fails since incorporating a 5G network architecture makes inequality worse. The results indicated a humanist social solidarity economic system (SSE) model that could mitigate the impact of this inequity. The SSE system model illustrates the relationship between social capital and the cohesiveness of a pluralistic society and proposes symbiotic mutualism as a means of achieving mutual prosperity. Additionally, it is a paradigm for social innovation that might mitigate the negative impacts of rural digitalization technology [4].

In this case, developing sustainable digital technology for rural regions necessitates creative business adjustments that better tackle social concerns. These improvements must also promote a human-economic, cultural, and ecological work ethic system that is more productive and efficient. Digital technology will inevitably emerge in rural areas; nevertheless, its negative impacts should be kept to a minimum. The SSE business model is one of the new institutional structures that can help lessen these adverse consequences because it makes use of local knowledge.

The SSE business model creates the value of new technical advancements in supporting sustainable rural development. Long-term implementation could assist achieve the SDGs' goals of lowering poverty, unemployment, and inequality by generating new, moral, and lucrative business opportunities.

The potential of local wisdom must be used in order to implement the SSE strategy. This is because growing the digital economy through platforms that are just concerned with financial inclusion as a new way to sell products and services is less humane and causes inequality and social instability. This dimension, which is likewise growing dynamically and becoming more complex, is challenging the quality and ability of public policy institutions for both national and international development. Due to the development of new 5G networks, information technology is convergent and may function more quickly than public institutions. Therefore, a new 5G network increases inequality in rural areas where human capital knowledge and capacity are lacking [5].

The framework is essential to a circular economy since it facilitates the accomplishment of the following SDGs:

1) High-quality digitalization connectivity in the production, consumption, market, and product growth systems is made available to rural entrepreneurial home business players through digital transformation.

2) Impact on entrepreneurs' total productivity. Institutional quality, capability, infrastructure spending, and regulation all play a part in the positive externalities and humane income development that benefit rural residents.

3) Impact on the development of new economic sectors founded on local expertise and cultural values, increasing productivity in the community [2].

There is no guarantee that the internet infrastructure and software will operate properly and efficiently or as intended, even though they have not been changed. This is a result of digital literacy communities not being given enough authority or attention. The inadequacies increase the gap in rural areas' adoption of digital technology. Digital literacy may increase, but the new economic model associated with the SSE transformation may not work out as intended. Understanding and implementing SSE's new business model will require time, effort, teamwork, and the integration of extra awareness. Social media and gaming are typically used to illustrate the increase in literacy and the usage of digital technologies. Few rural communities make timely and intentional use of this technology to meet their new economic needs. Furthermore, rather than manufacturing facilities, the majority of utilization is for online shopping led by consumers. This implies that the overall output has not improved noticeably. However, a small percentage of rural residents who are proficient in modern technology advance quickly, leaving many others behind and exacerbating the disparity that already exists. In the current era of digitization, family companies cannot compete with those that can put the new system into place [1].

The capacity of institutional and human resources should be improved by incorporating awareness of digital literacy into education and training related to digitalization-based social entrepreneurship. In this case, it is advantageous to have a future company strategy that depends on digital education and training. The high unemployment rate in the economy is partly caused by the workforce's lack of education and proficiency with regard to the foundations of digitalization. This implies that digitally based social entrepreneurship education and training are essential to increase overall effectiveness and production and reduce unemployment. As a result, FE (rural economic fundamentals) could help create more productive areas. This approach could be used to operationalize an ethnographic-based institutional policy with socioeconomic implications for developing regions [1, 5].

Consequently, a new entrepreneurial economic approach is needed, one that is founded on the SSE model of social innovation transformation system and the potential of local community wisdom. The new paradigm could be combined with

digital technology in sustainable villages to increase productivity and decrease inequality, unemployment, and poverty. The SSE model of social innovation has the ability to close the gap in social entrepreneurship theory since it is humanist in nature and different from the traditional materialistic capitalist socio-economic model. Therefore, social innovation in rural areas does not mean upending the status quo. However, it focuses on the number of social innovations that can coexist in pluralism for the benefit of the community [8].

Conclusion

The transition to digital technology has more complex and dynamic repercussions, both positive and bad. Its contribution to sustainable development cannot be sufficiently evaluated and requires international investigation. By creating business and well-paying job opportunities, digitalization technology boosts economic growth in rural areas. However, it has weakened well-being by increasing the financial disparity between people and families. In the first stage, technology increases unemployment faster than it creates new job opportunities.

The long-term advantages of digitization align with the increasing disparity it causes in rural regions. However, the new SSE transformation system model might be able to reduce this inequity to some extent based on the wisdom of the local humanist community. This is due to the fact that the models' traditional transformation function is a strategy to increase opportunities for decent work and lessen inequality. According to the SEE model, the objective and core values of a family social entrepreneur may not perfectly coincide with the current capitalist socioeconomic framework. Despite the pros and cons, digitalization technology should continue to advance toward a digital economy to mitigate the drawbacks.

By integrating digitalization technology into the SEE transformation, based on local expertise and social entrepreneurial potential, inequality may be lessened. However, it is difficult to generalize because the SSE concept is measured differently across populations. The measurement depends on how diverse the socio-cultural context of local wisdom is and how much potential it has. Research on the connection between the innovation and cultural diversity of successful entrepreneurship and the institutional development of family businesses is also becoming increasingly interesting. This implies that public digital security measures need to be given priority in order to regulate and reduce the main risks connected to digital entrepreneurship. Therefore, it is expected that this study would bridge the gap between new institutional theory and the literature on socio-cultural entrepreneurship.

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